

In-person session proposal for Vitae International Researcher Development Conference 2022

Name of proposer:	Brian Cahill
Job title:	Research Manager
Institution:	TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology
Country:	Germany
Professional biography:	Dr Brian Cahill is a Research Manager at the Learning and Skills Analytics Group of the Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology in Hannover/Germany, where he manages COST Action on Researcher Mental Health. After studying Mechanical Engineering in Ireland, he worked in Germany and Switzerland on application-oriented research related to microfluidics. He is a Member of the Governing Board of EuroScience and was Chair of the Marie Curie Alumni Association from March 2016 to February 2018.
Name, job title and institution of additional contributor/s:	Dr. Janet Metcalfe, Head, Vitae Prof. Melita Kovačević, Vice Rector for Research and Technology, University of Zagreb Dr. Adam Keszler, Managing Director, SciLink Foundation
What is the proposed format of your session?	Interactive activity
Abstract title	Exploring Practices to support Researcher Mental Wellbeing throughout Europe
Abstract for social activity	The ReMO COST Action on Researcher Mental Health is an international network that focuses on wellbeing and mental health within academia. The Researcher Mental Health and Well-Being Manifesto (Kismihok et al., 2021, https://zenodo.org/record/5559806) is a call to identify which practices and actions are effective at creating research environments that foster mental health and wellbeing, reduce mental health stigma, and empower researchers when it comes to well-being in their workplace. The ReMO COST Action provides a framework for involving a network of researchers, practitioners and institutional stakeholders in achieving the objectives of the Manifesto through designing actions and initiatives at the policy, institutional, community and individual levels. This session aims to leverage the experience of the audience with regard to how research institutions in the UK have addressed Researcher Mental Health with specific attention to the central place of mental health in the Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers (2019). The session will include a panel of speakers from throughout Europe who will discuss how societal awareness of mental health has led to greater willingness of researchers and many research stakeholders to recognise their responsibility to foster a positive research culture. The session will focus on the lessons that can be learned with regard to moving from raising awareness of researcher mental health towards involving institutions, funders, supervisors and researchers in developing practices that promote a healthy research environment and culture.
What are the outcomes of this session for participants?	Raising awareness of the prevalence of mental health issues Encouraging wider and systematic data collection on mental health issues

<p>Which theme does your session most closely relate to? How does your session relate to the conference theme(s)?</p>	<p>Collecting input from the participants as a basis for highlighting good practices based on their experience</p> <p>Cultures, environments, and impacts of researcher development</p> <p>This session relates to shaping an inclusive research environment and culture with regard to wellbeing and mental health that will engage research leaders, research managers, researcher developers, principal investigators and supervisors in professional development and nurturing the careers of researchers</p>
<p>Links to existing resources or background information that participants can use to prepare for your session</p>	<p>ReMO COST Action Website: https://projects.tib.eu/remo/ ReMO Working Group: https://e-services.cost.eu/action/CA19117/working-groups/apply ReMO Evidence Hub: https://www.zotero.org/groups/2521493/researcher_mental_health/library Researcher Mental Health and Well-being Manifesto https://zenodo.org/record/5788557 ReMO YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/channel/Uck2Bbj2eVm-AixJHOU_8jqQ ReMO Twitter Profile: https://twitter.com/ReMO_COST ReMO LinkedIn Account: https://www.linkedin.com/in/remo-cost-action/</p>
<p>How would your session be enhanced by taking place in person?</p>	<p>This session would benefit from an in person session to more effectively engage the experience of a diverse experienced audience of practitioners, career advisors, research managers, researchers, policy makers and research funders and comparing with international experience. ReMO is an international networking project and would benefit from the experience of the Vitae conference audience.</p>
<p>To help balance audience needs and interests across the programme, does your session relate specifically to?</p>	<p>A UK-specific policy or systemic issue, An internationally relevant policy or systemic issue, All researchers, Doctoral researchers or their supervisors, Research staff, managers or research leaders</p>
<p>Detailed session plan</p>	<p>The session will be an interactive workshop of 30-40 minutes. Each of the speakers will be given a limited time to introduce themselves and their main talking points. The session will take the form of a moderated discussion that will give a lot of space for audience participation and discussion. During the session notes will be taken and all the ideas will be recorded and used for a policy paper addressing researcher mental health.</p>